

Resilient Coasts Survey Results

Hesketh Bank

Resilient Coasts: Optimising Co-Benefit Solutions (Co-Opt) is an interdisciplinary research project involving the University of St Andrews, University of Liverpool, National Oceanography Centre and Cranfield University.

The postal survey aimed to explore the perceptions of coastal flood risk management and various coastal schemes in the UK. Co-Opt project aims to highlight what is required to support the implementation of green/nature-based solutions for flood risk management.

77 participants from Hesketh Bank, Banks and Tarleton (13% response rate)

48% 50%

8% aged 18-44

71% aged 45-74

20% aged 75 and above

Mean distance to the coast at Hesketh out Marsh = **3.02 km**

Mean distance to the River Douglas = **0.98 km**

experienced flooding and/or erosion

have noticed coastal change

concerned about climate change

have not heard about nature-based solutions

would accept managed realignment if people are not displaced

Top 3 preferred coastal flood risk protection strategies:

1 Planning restrictions

“Planning conditions are needed to prevent future inappropriate development in areas that should be turned over to natural processes as a method of defence”

2 A mix of options

“Mix of options based on data, research and trial projects”

3 Restoration/recreation of natural habitats

“Restoration/recreation of natural ecosystems such as salt marshes - we need to work with nature and this is an important area for wildlife”

More info about the project:
<https://projects.noc.ac.uk/co-opt/>

not confident they can influence local decisions

do not think the local authority is prepared well for coastal change

Trust rate among Hesketh Bank respondents (1=do not trust at all, 5=trust completely)

